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Synoptic and mesoscale winds in the complex terrain of Perdigão

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Abstract. For modeling complex atmospheric flows in wind energy studies when employing a chain of models, it is necessary to guarantee accurate wind simulations in all models that make up the chain. With this aim, we evaluated the ERA5 dataset (synoptic) and Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) simulations (mesoscale) of the wind over Perdigão, which will later serve as input to a microscale model. The Perdigão-2017 measurement campaign is one of the latest and largest experiments over a complex terrain, thus being a valuable dataset for the validation of atmospheric models. Previous long-term simulation studies in Perdigão did not employ a high-resolution reanalysis dataset for boundary conditions, nudging techniques, planetary boundary layer (PBL) sensitivity analysis, nor did compare synoptic and mesoscale data against local measurements. Here we simulated the wind in Perdigão using WRF with two one-way nested domains (9-km and 3-km horizontal resolutions) during 45 days, evaluating five PBL schemes. ERA5 reanalysis was used as input to the mesoscale simulations and for the spectral nudging in WRF's outer domain. Data from the top anemometer of a 100-m tower, located in Perdigão's SW ridge, were employed as reference in the evaluation of ERA5 and WRF wind speeds and directions. The hourly-averaged 3-km WRF simulations showed wind speed errors of 2.22 m/s RMSE and -0.02 m/s Bias with the YSU PBL scheme. The approximately 31-km ERA5 dataset exhibited total errors of 2.22 m/s (-0.37 m/s) RMSE (Bias). We attributed the similar ERA5 total error to its smoother wind speed values compared to WRF's, despite its coarser resolution, and not to its faithful representation of the wind in Perdigão. WRF overestimated wind speeds mainly between the NW and N sectors as a result of its misrepresentation of the NW mountain range. Despite ERA5 coarser resolution, its smoothed terrain did not seem to greatly affect the wind near the NW direction. Additionally, both ERA5 and WRF wind speed errors vary linearly with the measured wind speed.

1. Introduction

The latest and largest atmospheric measurement campaign over complex topography is Perdigão-2017, a double-hill site in Portugal's mainland [1]. Perdigão's relevance lies in the fact that complex terrains constitute a large part of the Earth's surface and are increasingly being used for wind exploration purposes, due to the depletion of flat terrains for the installation of wind farms [2]. Nevertheless, complex terrains induce phenomena in the wind that make their modeling more difficult than in simple (plain) terrains.

Long-term mesoscale simulations at Perdigão, which were later downscaled to the microscale, have employed as input the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Interim reanalysis (~ 79 km and 3 h of horizontal and temporal resolutions) [3] and ECMWF operational analysis (~ 8 km and 6 h of horizontal and temporal resolutions) [4]. However,

these simulations did not employ a high-resolution reanalysis dataset for boundary conditions, nudging techniques, planetary boundary layer (PBL) sensitivity analysis, or evaluated synoptic and mesoscale data with local measurements. Therefore, in this study, we used ERA5 (synoptic) reanalysis (~ 31 km and 1 h of horizontal and temporal resolutions) as input in the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model (mesoscale), in a nudged long-term simulation at Perdigão, also assessing the WRF PBL scheme that produces wind simulations with the smallest errors.

For modelling complex atmospheric flows in wind energy studies, a chain of models, encompassing global, meso, and microscale characteristics of the flow, is a recommended approach. Mesoscale data is used as input to microscale models in a model coupling approach. In turn, mesoscale models are fed by data from global models. Thus, to obtain precision in a local simulation, it is necessary to guarantee it in all models that make up the chain, since the flow in a site is composed of different atmospheric scale forcings. In this study, we evaluated the wind speed and direction obtained from ERA5 (global) and WRF (mesoscale) against anemometric measurements at 100 m height, to assess their characteristics at Perdigão.

2. Methodology

2.1. Site and measurement descriptions

From 1st May to 15th June of 2017 (the intense observational period, IOP), Perdigão field experiment took place in Portugal mainland [1]. The site is formed by two parallel ridges that span for 4 km in the NW-SE direction, distanced approximately 1.4 km, with an average height above sea level of 500 m and predominantly wind direction perpendicular to the orientation of the ridges [5].

The atmospheric large-scale systems that act on Perdigão are related to Serra da Estrela mountain range, 40 km to the northwest of Perdigão, and Serra Mamede, 60 km to the southeast. Additionally, in Perdigão, the atmospheric mesoscale systems are mainly thermally and orographically induced, with the occurrence of catabatic and anabatic winds, and those driven by the interaction of synoptic systems with the terrain [1].

Data from the 100-m tse04/T20 tower, located on the SW ridge, were employed in this work. Measurements of the sonic anemometer installed close to 100 m were used as reference for comparison with WRF and ERA5 data at Perdigão, in terms of average horizontal speed and wind direction. Acquired at the frequency of 20 Hz, the dataset (NCAR/EOL Quality Controlled High-rate ISFS surface flux data, geographic coordinate, tilt corrected, version 1.1 [6]) was further processed in hourly means. No additional filtering was applied to the measurements other than those carried out by UCAR/NCAR.

Two other 100-m towers were installed in Perdigão, one located in the valley (tse09/T25) and the other, in the NE ridge (tse13/T29). However, data from these towers were not used in this study, due to the WRF mesh not being able to represent the valley and to the similarity of the results obtained in the tse04/T20 tower compared to the tse13/T29.

2.2. WRF simulations

Perdigão simulations with the WRF model (version 4.2.1 [7]) were configured with two one-way nested domains, centered on the site, of 9-km (D01, Figure 1a) and 3-km (D02, Figure 1b) horizontal resolutions. Both domains had 100 vertical levels, and adaptive time steps were employed on the runs.

The main parameterizations chosen were: WRF Single-Moment 6-Class (WSM6) [8] microphysics scheme, Rapid Radiative Transfer Model (RRTM) [9] and Dudhia [10] for the long-wave and short-wave radiation, revised MM5 [11] scheme for the surface-layer (SL), Unified Noah [12] land surface scheme, Yonsei University (YSU) [13] for the planetary boundary layer (PBL), and Grell-Freitas [14] for cumulus. Apart from these parameterizations, a sensitivity

analysis was carried out where the following PBL-SL schemes were tested: YSU [13] with MM5 [11], Mellor–Yamada Nakanishi Niino (MYNN) Level 2.5 (MYNN2.5) with MYNN [15], Mellor–Yamada–Janjic (MYJ) with Eta Similarity [16], MYNN Level 3 (MYNN3) [17] with MYNN [15], and Asymmetric Convection Model 2 (ACM2) with MM5 [11].

Figure 1: WRF simulation domains, outer - D01 (a) and inner - D02 (b), and terrain representations. The red circle indicates Perdigão location.

Initial and boundary conditions were provided by ERA5 reanalysis [18], which was also employed for spectral nudging in the WRF outer domain since the 45 days were simulated in a single run (with a spin-up time of 24 hours). Orography was obtained from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) [19] near Perdigão and from the Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data (GMTED2010) [20] in the rest of the domains. Land cover classification was retrieved from CORINE Land Cover (CLC) 2012 [21], adapted to the United States Geological Survey (USGS) classification, according to [22], and employed in WRF together with NEWA land use lookup table [23]. Although the most recent CORINE database being CLC 2018, this was not used in this work, as this dataset was influenced by the extensive fire event that occurred in the region after the Perdigão measurement campaign.

The accuracy of WRF simulations and ERA5 reanalysis was assessed according to statistical metrics, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), systematic error (Bias), the difference between measured and estimated data, and the linear correlation coefficient (r). For comparison with the measured data, WRF output was horizontally interpolated, in a bi-linear way, at the equipment coordinates and vertically interpolated, in a linear way, at the reference equipment height; while the 100-m ERA5 data of the nearest grid point to tse04/T20 was chosen.

3. Results and Discussion

First, in order to obtain a better representation of the wind at the site through mesoscale modeling, a sensitivity analysis was carried out with WRF PBL schemes. According to the model constraints and previous studies, five simulations were performed and their results are presented in Table 1.

Compared with the wind speed at tower tse04/T20, YSU yields the lowest RMSE (2.22 m/s) and the highest r (0.64) values; whereas MYNN3 shows the highest value of RMSE (3.35 m/s)

and the lowest r (0.26). In addition, WRF with ACM2, displays a RMSE and r equals to 2.27 m/s and 0.63, close to the values of YSU, being both non-local PBL schemes. Regarding the wind speed Bias, the MYJ run presents the lowest value (0.01 m/s), but is closely followed by YSU simulation (-0.02 m/s). The highest Bias occur in the runs employing the MYNN versions, equal to 0.39 m/s with MYNN2.5 and 0.18 m/s with MYNN3. Based on these metrics, the following WRF results are obtained using the YSU PBL scheme, hereinafter referred to only as WRF simulation.

Table 1: Statistical metrics of the WRF PBL sensitivity analysis and ERA5 dataset of hourly-averaged wind speed estimations.

Dataset	RMSE [m/s]	Bias [m/s]	r
WRF YSU	2.22	-0.02	0.64
WRF MYNN2.5	2.67	0.39	0.57
WRF MYJ	3.15	0.01	0.27
WRF MYNN3	3.35	0.18	0.26
WRF ACM2	2.27	0.06	0.63
ERA5	2.22	-0.37	0.57

The estimated horizontal wind speeds, by ERA5 and WRF data, replicate, on average, the trends observed in the measurements, as depicted in Figure 2. Simulation errors calculated from hourly means are around 2.22 m/s of RMSE and -0.37 m/s of Bias for ERA5, and 2.22 m/s and -0.02 m/s for WRF, Table 1. Despite the similar total error of ERA5 compared to WRF, data from the synoptic and mesoscale models should be looked at carefully since these common statistical metrics have their values influenced by smooth solutions [24]. Nevertheless, the linear correlations with the tse04/T20 data are equal to 0.64 for WRF and 0.57 for ERA5.

The hourly error characteristics of the 3-km WRF compared to the approximately 31-km ERA5 do not exhibit the same trend over the 45 days. Some events can be highlighted when ERA5 estimates higher wind speed values and WRF correctly estimates the measured wind speed trend, as in the night/morning transitions of 01-02, 02-03, 08-09, and 10-11 of June (gray shading in Figure 2a). During these events, the wind speed at tower tse04/T20 is low (< 4 m/s) and the wind direction fluctuates overnight (Figure 2c). WRF is able to partially simulate the wind veer, however, the wind shift is not present in the ERA5 data. Conversely, there are no distinct events in which ERA5 presents a different wind speed trend than WRF and obtains lower errors. Additionally, in the hourly averages time series, the wind is frequently overestimated by WRF, visible in the peaks of Figure 2b, which represents the difference between the WRF and the tower wind velocities. While ERA5 values end up being closer to the ones measured in the tse04/T20 tower or underestimating the wind speed.

Aiming to assess the influence of the terrain on the mesoscale simulation, the wind rose of the 1-hour averaged wind speed difference, between WRF and tse04/T20 at 100 m a.g.l., is depicted in Figure 3. The image is overlaid in the terrain of the region, obtained by the SRTM data. WRF underpredictions are highest on the opposite sides of the wind rose, represented by dark blue, and in the wind directions perpendicular (NE and SW) and almost perpendicular (ENE and WSW) to the orientation of the ridges, with a greater frequency of high negative values in the NE sector. These are also the most frequently occurring wind directions, along with the W sector, during the IOP period. The larger positive differences between WRF and measured wind speeds happen from the NW to the N sectors, depicted by the orange and red colors in Figure 3, coinciding with the presence of mountain ranges. Thus, WRF overprediction in these directions is justified by the smoothed terrain representation in the mesoscale model. Furthermore, [4]

and [3] reported low roughness length values of the CORINE Land Cover for the Perdigão area, which does not agree with the local vegetation, and could contribute to the overestimation of the wind velocities by WRF. However, since in the higher frequency wind directions the over and under-predictions are, on average, low, the total error of the model is also low.

Figure 2: WRF, ERA5, and measured wind speed (a), wind speed difference (b), and wind direction (c) time series at tse04/T20, 1-hour averages at 100 m a.g.l.

ERA5 highest wind speed underestimations are shown in the NE direction and, less frequently, in ENE and SW, figure not shown here. The majority of ERA5 wind speed difference with

the data measured at tse04/T20 lies in the range between -3 m/s and 0 m/s. Wind speeds estimated above 3 m/s than the tower are not frequently observed in the ERA5 data and occur rarely between WNW and NW sectors.

Figure 3: Wind rose of the 1-hour averaged wind speed difference between WRF and tse04/T20, 100 m a.g.l., overlaid on the SRTM terrain representation.

Despite the higher horizontal resolution of WRF, ERA5 shows similar errors, which made us question the validity of point-wise verification metrics. Also, in Perdigão, as in many sites under complex wind flow, the atmospheric features are influenced by orographic characteristics, not represented in the models, and are highly localized, mainly under weak synoptic conditions. However, trying to discover more suitable statistical metrics for comparisons with the anemometric tower point measurements goes beyond the scope of this work.

Figure 4: Wind speed difference scatter plot between WRF, ERA5, and tse04/T20.

In terms of the hourly differences between the wind speed of WRF and the tower and of ERA5 and the tower, Figure 4 exhibits that both differences can be linearly correlated with the measured wind speed values in tse04/T20 (WS_T). At low 100-m wind speeds (< 5 m/s), the model and the dataset tend to predict higher wind speed values than the measurements; while at higher 100-m wind speeds, WRF and ERA5 underpredict the wind speed. Conversely, the difference between the WRF and ERA5 estimated values tends to increase with higher 100-m wind speeds.

4. Conclusions

Through a sensitivity analysis of WRF PBL schemes, the YSU simulation yielded the lowest RMSE and higher linear correlation, between the five tested schemes, with the tse04/T20 measurements. In addition, the two non-local PBL schemes (YSU and ACM2) exhibited lower RMSE and higher r values than the three tested local schemes (MYJ, MYNN2.5, and MYNN3).

The 3-km WRF YSU simulation showed total errors equal to 2.22 m/s RMSE and -0.02 m/s Bias in hourly means, while the approximately 31-km ERA5 data exhibited 2.22 m/s and -0.37 m/s RMSE and Bias errors. Also, both ERA5 and WRF wind speed errors displayed a negative linear correlation with the measured wind speed at tse04/T20. Although similar total errors were depicted in the global data, compared to the mesoscale simulation, this does not mean a similar accuracy of the ERA5 dataset and WRF output along the analyzed period (45 days) at Perdigão. In fact, ERA5 presented smoother wind speed values in comparison to WRF, without extreme peaks and valleys in the time series, thus explaining its low total errors.

WRF showed higher wind speed overestimations than ERA5, mainly between NW and N sectors, suggested by the misrepresentation of the NW mountain range. ERA5 dataset, despite its coarser resolution than the mesoscale model, did not seem to be greatly affected by the smoothed terrain near the NW direction. Additionally, four late night/early morning episodes were highlighted, where WRF was able to correctly predict the wind speed and veer and ERA5 did not, suggesting the main influence of mesoscale forcings in Perdigão during these events.

In a future work, the WRF results will be used as input to a microscale model and wind data of the three atmospheric scales (global, meso, and micro) will be evaluated.

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